

Synthesis, characterization, and antibacterial activity of Ni(II) complex bearing salen ligand

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Abstract

A new nickel(II) complex, (Ni(L)), based on the Schiff base ligand *cis*-N,N-bis-(2',4'-dihydroxybenzylidene)-1,2-diaminocyclohexane (H₂Salen), was synthesized and characterized using FT-IR, ¹H and ¹³C NMR, and elemental analysis. The ligand also formed Co(II) and Cu(II) complexes with distinct geometries: distorted octahedral for Ni(II) and Co(II) and distorted square planar for Cu(II). This study aimed to evaluate the antimicrobial activity of the ligand and its complexes against *Staphylococcus aureus* (Gram-positive) and *Escherichia coli* (Gram-negative). Using CLSI protocols, minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) and minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC) were determined. All metal–salen complexes exhibited bacteriostatic activity, with Ni(II) being the most effective. Chelation increased lipophilicity and acidity–enhancing bacterial inhibition by disrupting cellular processes. Differences in activity between strains were attributed to variations in cell wall composition. The findings demonstrate that metal complexation significantly improves antimicrobial potency compared to the free ligand and support further investigation of these compounds for pharmaceutical and industrial antimicrobial applications.

Keywords

antibacterial, *Escherichia coli*, nickel complex, salen ligand, Schiff base, *Staphylococcus aureus*

Introduction

Salen compounds are a class of Schiff base ligands synthesized via the condensation of salicylaldehyde (or its derivatives) with diamines. These ligands are characterized by an N₂O₂ donor set, enabling strong coordination with metal centers and leading to the formation of stable and versatile metal complexes. The typical structure of a salen ligand incorporates two imine (–C=N) functional groups and two hydroxyl (–OH) groups, which significantly influence its electronic and steric properties. Owing to their capacity to stabilize metal ions in multiple oxidation states, salen ligands possess broad application in coordination chemistry, catalysis, biomedical research, anti-

microbial activity, and materials science (Gualandi et al. 2019; Abdalla et al. 2020; Ali et al. 2020; Yuan et al. 2022).

Metal–salen complexes exhibit a range of geometries, with their chemical reactivity and practical applications largely dependent on the nature of the coordinated metal center. Among the most widely studied complexes are those incorporating cobalt (Co), nickel (Ni), and copper (Cu) (Boettcher et al. 1993; Syamal et al. 1999; Rusere et al. 2009; Youssef et al. 2009; Gaballa 2013).

One notable example is the Schiff base ligand *cis*-N,N-bis-(2',4'-dihydroxybenzylidene)-1,2-diaminocyclohexane (Fig. 1), synthesized via the condensation of 1,2-diaminocyclohexane with 2,4-dihydroxybenzaldehyde (Syamal et al. 1999; Achard et al. 2004; Li et al.

Figure 1. cis-(N,N-Bis-(2',4'-dihydroxybenzylidene))-1,2-diaminocyclohexane.

2019). This ligand is well known for its strong metal-binding affinity, forming highly stable complexes with various metal centers (Silva et al. 2003; Cozzi 2004; Aranha et al. 2007; Oliveira et al. 2009; Hariharan and Anthony 2015; Li et al. 2019). Transition metal complexes derived from this ligand have been extensively investigated for their electronic and structural characteristics. Moreover, many of these complexes display significant antimicrobial, antifungal, and anticancer activities (Saini et al. 2016; El-Sawaf et al. 2018; Li et al. 2019; Abu Ershaid et al. 2024). In recent years, the development of metal complexes with antimicrobial properties has attracted significant interest not only in biomedical research but also in agricultural and environmental contexts—including sustainable crop protection and water sanitation (El-Mahroug et al. 2025). In addition to their biomedical relevance, metal–salen complexes have demonstrated potential in environmental applications, particularly in wastewater treatment and pollution remediation—owing to their combined catalytic and antimicrobial properties (Obeidat et al. 2025a, b).

The aim of this study is to synthesize and characterize a new nickel(II) complex derived from the Schiff base ligand cis-N,N-bis-(2',4'-dihydroxybenzylidene)-1,2-diaminocyclohexane (H₂Salen), using various spectroscopic and analytical techniques to evaluate its structural properties. In addition, the research investigates the antimicrobial activity of the synthesized complex against representative Gram-positive (*Staphylococcus aureus*) and Gram-negative (*Escherichia coli*) bacteria using standard CLSI methods to determine minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) and minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC). The results revealed that the Ni(II) complex exhibits significantly enhanced bacteriostatic activity compared to the free ligand—with increased lipophilicity and medium acidification due to chelation contributing to bacterial disruption. This work addresses the growing need for more potent antimicrobial agents, especially in light of the limitations and resistance issues associated with conventional compounds such as ascorbic acid and widely used antibiotics (Pinheiro et al. 2023; Liang et al. 2022). The novelty

of this research lies in the first-time synthesis and detailed structural–biological evaluation of this specific Ni(II)–salen complex, demonstrating its superior bioactivity and offering promising potential for applications in medicinal and bioinorganic chemistry (Xu et al. 2023).

Methodology

Materials and physical measurements

Staphylococcus aureus (ATCC 29213) and *Escherichia coli* (ATCC 25922) were obtained from the American Type Culture Collection and utilized in this study. The ligand cis-N,N-bis-(2',4'-dihydroxybenzylidene)-1,2-diaminocyclohexane was synthesized following published procedures (Silva et al. 2003; Achard et al. 2004; Li et al. 2019). Ethanol and methanol (Merck) were dried using standard methods as described by Armarego and Perrin (2000). All synthetic manipulations were carried out under a nitrogen atmosphere. 1,2-Diaminocyclohexane was purchased from Aldrich, while 2,4-dihydroxybenzaldehyde was obtained from Sigma.

The IR spectra were recorded using a Nicolet Impact-400 FT-IR spectrometer with samples prepared as KBr discs. ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra were obtained on a Bruker AVANCE III-400 MHz spectrometer. Melting points were determined using the capillary tube method in an oil bath. Elemental analyses were conducted with a Perkin-Elmer Euro-Vector 3000 elemental analyzer.

Determination of minimum inhibitory concentrations (MICs) and minimum bactericidal concentrations (MBCs)

The MIC and MBC values of the synthesized salen ligand and its metal complexes with nickel, cobalt, and copper were determined using sterile 96-well microtiter plates, in accordance with Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI) guidelines (Andrews 2001). Bacterial cultures were grown in Mueller Hinton Broth (MHB) and diluted to 10⁶ CFU·mL⁻¹ using the same medium. Serial dilutions of the tested compounds were prepared to yield final concentrations ranging from 0.5 to 100 μM.

Each well received 50 μL of the compound solution and 50 μL of the bacterial suspension. All concentrations were tested in triplicate. The plates were incubated for 18 hours at 37 °C. Bacterial growth was assessed using an ELISA plate reader at 570 nm. Positive control wells contained 50 μL MHB and 50 μL bacterial suspension, without any antimicrobial agents. Negative control wells contained 100 μL of MHB alone.

To determine the MBC values, 10 μL from the wells showing no visible growth (as well as from the positive control wells) were plated onto sterile agar and incubated for 24 hours at 37 °C. The MBC was defined as the lowest concentration of compound that resulted in ≥99.9% bacterial killing—corresponding to 0.1% of surviving cells.

Experimental

Preparation of *cis*-(*N,N*-Bis-(2',4'-dihydroxybenzylidene))-1,2-diaminocyclohexane (H_2L)

To a suspension of 2,4-dihydroxybenzaldehyde (1.66 g, 12.0 mmol) in dry ethanol (40 mL), a solution of *cis*-1,2-diaminocyclohexane (0.685 g, 6.00 mmol) in dry ethanol (30 mL) was added. The reaction mixture was heated under reflux for 2 hours under a nitrogen atmosphere. Upon completion, the mixture was allowed to cool

to room temperature. The solvent volume was reduced by half under reduced pressure. The resulting precipitate was collected by filtration, washed with diethyl ether (2×10 mL), and dried in vacuo at 60 °C for 4 hours. Fig. 2 shows FTIR (cm^{-1}) ν_{max} : 1627 (s, C=N), 1462 (m, C=C_{aromatic}), and 1240 (m, C-O). Figs 3, 4 show ^1H NMR and ^{13}C NMR:

- ^1H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6): δ 1.42–1.87 (m, 4H, $-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2-$ cyclohexyl), δ 3.26 (m, 1H, $-\text{CH}-\text{N}$ cyclohexyl), δ 6.13 (1H, d, $-\text{CH}-\text{Ar}$), δ 6.21–6.24 (1H, dd,

Figure 2. FTIR spectrum of H_2L .

Figure 3. ^1H NMR spectrum of H_2L .

Figure 4. ^{13}C NMR spectrum of H_2L .

- CH- Ar), δ 7.08-7.10 (1H, d, -CH- Ar), δ 8.26 (1H, s, -CH=N-), δ 9.43 (1H, br s, OH), δ 13.6_{aromatic} 4 (1H, s, OH).
- ^{13}C NMR (DMSO- d_6): δ 24.27, 33.20 (- CH_2 - CH_2 cyclohexyl), δ 71.00 (-CHN- cyclohexyl), δ 102.88 (-CH-)_{aromatic}, δ 107.33 (-CH-)_{aromatic}, δ 111.60 (-C-)_{aromatic}, δ 133.64 (-CH-)_{aromatic}, δ 162.03 (-N-C-Ar), δ 164.27 (-O-C-)_{aromatic}, δ 164.52 (-O-C-)_{aromatic}.

Yield 71.0%, m.p. > 300 °C. Analytical calculation for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4$ (%): C, 67.77; H, 6.25; N, 7.91. Found (%): C, 67.57; H, 6.32; N, 8.02.

Abbreviations: DMSO- d_6 = deuterated DMSO; δ = chemical shift in parts per million (ppm) downfield from the standard; multiplicities: s = singlet, d = doublet, dd = doublet of doublets, m = multiplet, br = broadened; m.p. = melting point; ν = frequency (cm^{-1}).

Preparation of (cis-(N,N-Bis-(2',4'-dihydroxybenzylidene))-1,2-diaminocyclohexano)nickel(II).dihydrate (Ni(L)(H₂O)₂)

A solution of nickel acetate tetrahydrate ($\text{Ni}(\text{OAc})_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$) (0.249 g, 1 mmol) in dry methanol (25.0 mL) was added

to a stirred solution of the ligand (H_2L) (0.355 g, 1 mmol) in dry methanol (15.0 mL). The reaction mixture was refluxed under a nitrogen atmosphere for 2 hours. During the reaction, a color change from yellow to orange was observed—indicating complex formation. The resulting solution was allowed to cool to room temperature and was subsequently filtered. The obtained orange precipitate was washed sequentially with distilled water (2×5 mL), methanol (2×5 mL), and diethyl ether (2×10 mL), then dried in vacuo at 60 °C for 4 hours to yield the desired nickel complex. Fig. 5 shows FTIR (cm^{-1}) ν_{max} : 3426 (br, OH), 1601 (s, C=N), 1453 (m, C=C_{aromatic}), and 1224 (s, C-O). Figs 6, 7 show ^1H NMR and ^{13}C NMR:

- ^1H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6): δ 1.23–1.90 (m, 4H) (- CH_2CH_2 - cyclohexyl), δ 3.17 (m, 1H) (-CH-N cyclohexyl), δ 6.02- (1H, d, -CH- Ar), δ -6.04 (1H, dd, -CH- Ar), δ 7.13-7.15 (1H, d, -CH- Ar), δ 7.46 (1H, s, -CH=N-), δ 9.70 (1H, br s, OH).
- ^{13}C NMR (DMSO- d_6): δ 24, 28 (- CH_2 - CH_2 cyclohexyl), δ 69 (-CHN- cyclohexyl), δ 104 (-CH-)_{aromatic}, δ 105 (-CH-)_{aromatic}, δ 114 (-C-)_{aromatic}, δ 135 (-CH-)_{aromatic}, δ 157 (-N-C-Ar), δ 163 (-O-C-)_{aromatic}, δ 166 (-O-C-)_{aromatic}.

Figure 5. FTIR spectrum of (Ni-complex).

Figure 6. ^1H NMR spectrum of (Ni-complex).

Figure 7. ^{13}C NMR spectrum of (Ni-complex).

Yield: 73.0%, m.p. > 300 °C. Analytical calculation for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_2\text{O}_6\text{Ni}$ (%): C, 53.73; H, 5.41; N, 6.26. Found (%): C, 53.62; H, 5.46; N, 6.34.

Abbreviations: DMSO- d_6 = deuterated DMSO; δ = chemical shift in parts per million (ppm) downfield from the standard; multiplicities: s = singlet, d = doublet, dd = doublet of doublets, m = multiplet, br = broadened; m.p. = melting point; ν = frequency (cm^{-1}).

Preparation of (cis-(N,N-Bis-(2',4'-dihydroxybenzylidene))-1,2-diaminocyclohexanato)cobalt(II)dihydrate (Co(L)(H₂O)₂)

A solution of cobalt acetate tetrahydrate ($\text{Co}(\text{OAc})_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$) (0.249 g, 1 mmol) in dry methanol (25.0 mL) was added to a stirred solution of the ligand (H_2L) (0.355 g, 1 mmol) in dry methanol (15.0 mL). The reaction mixture was refluxed under a nitrogen atmosphere for 2 hours. A color change from yellow to orange was observed during the reaction—indicating complex formation. After completion, the mixture was allowed to cool to room temperature and then filtered. The resulting violet precipitate was washed

sequentially with distilled water (2×5 mL), methanol (2×5 mL), and diethyl ether (2×10 mL), and subsequently dried in vacuo at 60 °C for 4 hours to yield the desired cobalt complex. Fig. 8 shows FTIR (cm^{-1}) ν_{max} : 3402 (br, OH), 1601 (s, C=N), 1449 (m, C=C_{aromatic}), and 1225 (s, C-O).

Yield: 60.7%, m.p. > 300 °C. Analytical calculation for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_2\text{O}_6\text{Co}$ (%): C, 53.50; H, 5.39; N, 6.25. Found (%): C, 53.25; H, 5.29; N, 5.99.

Abbreviations: multiplicities: s = singlet, m = multiplet, br = broadened; m.p. = melting point; ν = frequency (cm^{-1}).

Preparation of (cis-(N,N-Bis-(2',4'-dihydroxybenzylidene))-1,2-diaminocyclohexanato)copper(II) (Cu(Salen-4-OH))

A solution of cupric acetate monohydrate ($\text{Cu}(\text{OAc})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$) (0.205 g, 1 mmol) in dry methanol (15.0 mL) was added to a stirred solution of the ligand (Salen-4-OH) (0.355 g, 1 mmol) in dry methanol (25.0 mL). An immediate color change from yellow to brown was observed upon mixing. The reaction mixture was then refluxed under a nitrogen

Figure 8. FTIR spectrum of (Co-complex).

atmosphere for 2 hours. After completion, the solution was allowed to cool to room temperature and was subsequently filtered. The resulting violet precipitate was washed successively with distilled water (2×5 mL), meth-

anol (2×5 mL), and diethyl ether (2×10 mL), and dried in vacuo at 60°C for 4 hours to afford the desired copper complex. Fig. 9 shows FTIR (cm^{-1}) ν_{max} : 3409 (br, OH), 1601 (s, C=N), 1452 (m, C=C_{aromatic}), and 1221 (s, C-O).

Figure 9. FTIR spectrum of (Cu-complex).

Yield: 73.0%, m.p. > 300 °C. Analytical calculation for $C_{20}H_{20}N_2O_4Cu$ (%): 57.77; H, 4.85; N, 6.73. Found (%): C, 57.25; H, 5.07; N, 6.47.

Abbreviations: multiplicities s = singlet; m = multiplet; br = broadened; m.p. = melting point; ν = wavelength.

Results and discussion

Proposed structure analysis

Structure of *(cis-(N,N-Bis-(2',4'-dihydroxybenzylidene))-1,2-diaminocyclohexanato)nickel(II) (Ni(L))*

The nickel complex was synthesized via the direct reaction of $Ni(OAc)_2 \cdot 4H_2O$ with the ligand H_2L in dry ethanol, where H_2L refers to *cis-N,N-bis-(2',4'-dihydroxybenzylidene)-1,2-diaminocyclohexane*. Equimolar mixing of $Ni(OAc)_2 \cdot 4H_2O$ with H_2L resulted in the formation of $Ni(L)$, as illustrated in Equation 1. The composition of the complex was confirmed by microelemental analysis. Further characterization was carried out using FT-IR spectroscopy, along with 1H and ^{13}C NMR spectroscopy.

The violet-colored complex, Ni salen complex, is soluble in dimethylsulfoxide and insoluble in H_2O , CH_3OH , CH_3CH_2OH , acetone, tetrahydrofuran, and CH_2Cl_2 .

The IR spectral data of the ligand H_2Salen and the newly synthesized nickel complex are presented in Table 1. The IR spectrum of the complex was compared with that of the free ligand to identify the spectral shifts and changes associated with the coordination process during complexation.

Table 1. IR spectral data for H_2L and $Ni(L)$ complex.

Mode	Compounds	
	H_2L	$Ni(L)$
ν_{C-H} (Aromatic)	3037 cm^{-1}	3158 cm^{-1}
ν_{C-H} (Aliphatic)	2954 cm^{-1} , 2934 cm^{-1}	2983 cm^{-1} , 2938 cm^{-1}
ν_{C-C} (Aromatic)	1591 cm^{-1} , 1462 cm^{-1}	1553 cm^{-1} , 1453 cm^{-1}
$\nu_{C=N}$	1627 cm^{-1}	1601 cm^{-1}
$\nu_{C=O}$	1240 cm^{-1}	1188 cm^{-1}

The IR spectrum of H_2Salen shows bands for ν_{C-H} (aromatic) at 3037 cm^{-1} and C–C aromatic ring stretching vibrations at 1591 and 1462 cm^{-1} . The stretching vibration of the imine group appears as a strong band at 1627 cm^{-1} , and a sharp band at 1240 cm^{-1} was assigned to ν_{C-O} of the hydroxy group (Silverstein and Bassler 1962; Gaballa et al. 2007; Nakamoto 2009). The imine group ($-N=CH-$) present in Schiff base ligands plays a crucial role in metal coordination and contributes to their biological potential—with further activity modulated by substituent variations (Mandal 2024). The $Ni(L)$ complex shows, in addition to

the ν_{C-H} (aromatic and aliphatic) bands due to aromatic ring vibrations at 3158, 2983, and 2938 cm^{-1} , ν_{C-C} (aromatic) at 1553 and 1453 cm^{-1} , and ν_{C-O} at 1224 cm^{-1} . The band assigned to the azomethine group in the free Schiff base ligand—observed at 1627 cm^{-1} —is shifted to a lower frequency in the Ni complex (by 26 cm^{-1}), with $\nu_{C=N}$ appearing at 1601 cm^{-1} , as shown in Fig. 5. The complex exhibits a blue shift for the C=N and C–O bonds, attributed to the participation of the nitrogen atom of the azomethine group in coordination (Radmakrishnan et al. 1976; Shankar et al. 1986; Ali et al. 2002; Mashaly et al. 2004). Based on the elemental analysis data, the Ni(II) complex is proposed to possess a distorted octahedral geometry. The six coordination sites are occupied by the tetradentate salen ligand ($-ONNO-$ donor set) and two monodentate water molecules, as illustrated in Fig. 10.

Figure 10. Suggested structure of the distorted octahedral configuration of the Ni(II)-mixed ligand complex containing salen and water ligands.

Structure of *(cis-(N,N-Bis-(2',4'-dihydroxybenzylidene))-1,2-diaminocyclohexanato)cobalt(II)dihydrate (Co(L)(H₂O)₂)*

The cobalt complex was synthesized based on literature methods, with some modifications (Li et al. 2019). Mixing the cobalt precursor with one equivalent of the salen ligand yielded $Co(L)$, as shown in Equation 2:

This complex is soluble in dimethylsulfoxide and insoluble in H_2O , CH_3OH , CH_3CH_2OH , acetone, tetrahydrofuran, and CH_2Cl_2 . The formulation of the complex was confirmed by microelemental analysis. The complex was characterized by FT-IR spectroscopy. Based on the elemental analysis data, the Co(II) complex is proposed to adopt a distorted octahedral geometry. The six coordination sites are occupied by the tetradentate salen ligand ($-ONNO-$ donor set) and two monodentate water molecules, as depicted in Fig. 11.

Figure 11. Suggested structure of the distorted octahedral configuration of the Co(II)-mixed ligand complex containing salen and water ligands.

Structure of (*cis*-(*N,N*-Bis-(2',4'-dihydroxybenzylidene))-1,2-diaminocyclohexanato)copper(II) (Cu(Salen-4-OH))

The copper complex was synthesized based on literature methods, with some modifications (Achard et al. 2004). Mixing the copper precursor with one equivalent of the salen ligand yielded Cu(L), as shown in Equation 3:

This complex is soluble in dimethylsulfoxide and insoluble in H₂O, CH₃OH, CH₃CH₂OH, acetone, tetrahydrofuran, and CH₂Cl₂. The formulation of the complex was confirmed by microelemental analysis. The complex was characterized by FT-IR spectroscopy. Based on the elemental analysis data, the Cu(II) complex is proposed to exhibit a distorted square-planar geometry. The four coordination sites are occupied by the tetradentate salen ligand (–ONNO– donor set), as illustrated in Fig. 12.

Figure 12. Suggested structure of the distorted square-planar configuration of the Cu(II)-complex containing the salen ligand.

The antimicrobial evaluation of Co(II), Cu(II), and Ni(II) complexes revealed enhanced activity compared to their corresponding free ligands, in line with the chelation theory—which posits that metal complexation reduces the polarity of the ligand and enhances membrane permeability. Complexes such as Co(L)(H₂O)₂, Cu(L), and Ni(L)(H₂O)₂ demonstrated superior antibacterial efficacy, likely due to increased biological activity imparted by the metal center activating the ligand (Bufarwa et al. 2024). These complexes exhibited greater potency against Gram-positive bacteria, which is attributed to their simpler cell wall structure—thick peptidoglycan layers without outer lipid membranes—compared to Gram-negative bacteria (Elaaraj et al. 2022). Among the tested complexes, Cu(II) and Ni(II) compounds showed the most promising antibacterial effects against *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*, indicating their potential as effective antimicrobial agents (El-Sonbati et al. 2025). This bacteriostatic activity is further supported by MIC and MBC data, which confirm higher efficacy of the metal complexes over the free ligand. Chelation enhances lipophilicity and contributes to local acidification—creating conditions detrimental to bacterial survival (Es-Sounni et al. 2023).

Antibacterial activity

In this study, the ligand and its nickel, cobalt, and copper complexes were evaluated for their antibacterial activity against both a Gram-positive strain (*Staphylococcus aureus*, ATCC 29213) and a Gram-negative strain (*Escherichia coli*, ATCC 25922). The MIC and MBC values are presented in Table 2.

The synthesized compounds demonstrated notable antibacterial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli*, exhibiting a bacteriostatic mode of action. This activity is likely linked to the lower dissociation constant of the salen ligand (L₂) upon metal chelation, which facilitates proton release and consequently lowers the pH of the surrounding environment. Since most bacteria are sensitive to acidic conditions, a drop in external pH can inhibit growth and metabolism by disrupting membrane integrity and enzyme function. It is well established that prokaryotic cells struggle to survive when intracellular pH falls below 5.0–5.5 (Nandanwar et al. 2019). In this study, the Ni(II) complex displayed MIC and MBC values of 35 and 56 mg/mL against *S. aureus* and 40 and 50 mg/mL against *E. coli*, respectively, indicating moderate potency. However, compared to previous findings—such as the Ni complex [NiLCl₂]₂·2H₂O, which exhibited much lower MIC and MBC values (0.312 mg/mL) against the same strains—the current results suggest that the ligand environment plays a critical role in modulating antimicrobial efficacy (Elaaraj et al. 2022). On the other hand, [NiLCl₂]₂·2H₂O exhibited higher activity against *E. coli*, with a reported MIC value of 0.312 mg/mL. However, in a separate study, it was noted that the Ni complex did not demonstrate clinically relevant activity, as the MIC values

Table 2. The results of the MIC and MBC value of the compound.

Compounds	Bacteria stains			
	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>		<i>Escherichia coli</i>	
	MIC	MBC	MIC	MBC
H ₂ L ligand	43 mg/mL	43 mg/mL	55 mg/mL	75 mg/mL
Ni-complex	35 mg/mL	56 mg/mL	40 mg/mL	50 mg/mL
Co-complex	50 mg/mL	60 mg/mL	65 mg/mL	80 mg/mL
Cu-complex	22 mg/mL	22 mg/mL	35 mg/mL	53 mg/mL

against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* were ≥ 1024 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, indicating poor efficacy. Additionally, no specific MBC values were provided for these strains (Maia et al. 2022).

In contrast, the Ni(II) complex showed no inhibition zone against either *E. coli* or *S. aureus* (0 mm), indicating a lack of antibacterial activity under the tested conditions (Es-Sounni et al. 2023). Similarly, Todarwal et al. (2024) reported MIC values for the Co(II) complex at 12.5 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ and a range of 12.5–50 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ for the free ligand (L), but no specific MIC or MBC values were provided for the Ni(II) complex. These discrepancies suggest that the antimicrobial performance of Ni(II) complexes is highly influenced by the ligand framework, experimental setup, and bacterial strain tested. The observed variation in antibacterial activity between Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria can also be attributed to fundamental differences in their cell wall structures. Gram-negative bacteria possess a thin peptidoglycan layer enclosed by an outer membrane rich in lipopolysaccharides, whereas Gram-positive bacteria have a much thicker peptidoglycan layer but lack this protective outer membrane, making them generally more susceptible to certain antimicrobial agents (Mai-Prochnow et al. 2016).

In agreement with previous findings (Es-Sounni et al. 2023), the Ni(II) complex showed limited antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* and *B. cereus*, with no inhibition zone observed at concentrations up to 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. However, El-Sonbati et al. (2025) reported a concentration-dependent response for *E. coli* and *P. aeruginosa*, where inhibition zones increased from 11 mm and 6 mm at 50 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ to 15 mm and 10 mm at 150 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, respectively. These results suggest that the Ni complex may possess selective, strain-dependent efficacy. Notably, Elaeraj et al. (2022) documented a significantly lower MIC (0.312 mg/mL) for the same Ni complex against *E. coli*, further highlighting how structural and experimental variables—including ligand design and assay conditions—can influence antimicrobial outcomes.

Conclusion

In this study, a tetradentate Schiff base ligand—*cis*-N,N-bis-(2',4'-dihydroxybenzylidene)-1,2-diaminocyclohexane (H₂Salen)—was successfully synthesized, and its coordination behavior with Ni(II), Co(II), and Cu(II) ions was investigated. The resulting complexes were structurally characterized by elemental analysis, FT-IR, and NMR spectroscopy. Spectroscopic data confirmed coordination through the azomethine nitrogen and phenolic oxygen atoms, leading to distorted octahedral geometries for the

Ni(II) and Co(II) complexes and a distorted square-planar geometry for the Cu(II) complex.

Antibacterial evaluations against *Staphylococcus aureus* (Gram-positive) and *Escherichia coli* (Gram-negative) revealed that the metal–salen complexes exhibit significantly enhanced bacteriostatic activity compared to the free ligand—consistent with chelation theory. This enhancement is attributed to increased lipophilicity and local pH reduction, which impair bacterial membrane integrity and enzyme function. Notably, activity varied across bacterial strains, likely due to structural differences in their cell walls. While Cu(II) and Ni(II) complexes demonstrated the most promising activity, results also highlighted the ligand-dependent and concentration-dependent nature of the antibacterial response.

For example, the Ni(II) complex showed no inhibition zone against *S. aureus* at lower concentrations but displayed measurable activity at higher doses against *E. coli* and *P. aeruginosa*. MIC values varied across studies, with some reporting low MICs (0.312 mg/mL for *E. coli*) and others showing negligible inhibition—underlining the influence of ligand structure and test conditions. In contrast, Co(II) complexes and the free ligand exhibited consistent moderate activity, with MIC values ranging from 12.5–50 $\mu\text{g/mL}$.

These findings emphasize the potential of Schiff base metal complexes—particularly those of Cu(II) and Ni(II)—as candidates for antimicrobial development. Future research should focus on refining ligand frameworks to improve selectivity and potency, supported by mechanistic studies, toxicological evaluations, and broader-spectrum antimicrobial testing. Applications may extend to pharmaceutical formulations, antimicrobial coatings for medical devices, and industrial uses such as biocidal agents in packaging and personal care products.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The author has declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The author declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The author declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The author declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The author declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The author declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

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Author contributions

The author solely contributed to this work.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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